

Alkylation of aniline over base zeolites

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Vapour phase alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol over Li, Na, K, Ca, Sr and Ba ion exchanged zeolites at atmospheric pressure gives *N*-alkylated and *C*-alkylated anilines. The *N*-alkylation selectivity increases with increase in basicity of the zeolite. The major product is the *ortho*-isomer. The effect of the basic nature of catalyst on the conversion and product selectivity has been evaluated. Co-existence of the acidic and basic sites in the alkali cation exchanged zeolites enhances the *N*-alkylation rather than the ring alkylation.

The alkali cation exchanged zeolites have good catalytic activity in dehydration of alcohol¹ and isomerisation of *n*-butenes². Alkylation of alkylbenzene alkali cation exchanged zeolites has been studied^{3,4}. Zeolites have been used for the alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol^{5,6}. The main purpose of this work is to investigate the effect of base zeolites on product selectivity and to evaluate their catalytic activity in the alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol.

Results and Discussion

Alkylation of aniline with isopropanol over alkali and alkaline earth metal ion exchanged zeolites was studied in vapour phase under atmospheric pressure. The results are listed in Table 1. Both *N*-alkylated and *C*-alkylated prod-

ucts were obtained : *N*-isopropylaniline, *O*-isopropylaniline and *p*-isopropylaniline. Among the *C*-alkylated products, the yield of *ortho*-isomer is more than *para*-isomer. This preferential selectivity towards *ortho*-isomer is presumably due to the proximity of the alkylating group on the surface of the catalyst to the *ortho*-position of aniline. The yields of the ring alkylated products were found more than those of *N*-alkylated product over Li-Y zeolite. This *C*-alkylation selectivity is attributed to the weak acidity of Li-Y zeolite. All the catalysts are of acidic nature though rather weak; the catalysts containing lithium ion have stronger acidic nature than the others. The activity of potassium ion exchanged zeolite was found higher than that of lithium and sodium ion exchanged zeolites. *N*-Alkylation selectivity gradually increased from Li-Y to K-Y zeolite. Alkali ion exchanged zeolites behave as base catalyst showing the basic character of alkali metal. If two kinds of cations exist in a zeolite then different active sites would be expected. The basic sites of alkali ion exchanged zeolites are believed to be $(\text{AlO}_4)^-$ paired with alkali ions. The basicity of $(\text{AlO}_4)^-$ would be enhanced by Na and K ions⁷. The main characteristic feature of zeolites is the lower activity as the cations become less electronegative from Li to K and Ca to Sr; hence, the charge on framework oxygen (their base strength) increases in the order, $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K}$. The *N*-alkylation was found to increase with increase in basic nature of the ions. The catalysts with much stronger acidic sites catalyse the *C*-alkylation. It has been reported that *N*-alkylation and *C*-alkylation proceed on the Ce-Y and H-Y zeolites respectively⁵. It was observed that propene was formed during the reaction between aniline and isopropanol. Propene was formed by the dehydration of isopropanol over the catalyst in a parallel reaction. This proves that basic zeolites certainly have acidic properties. *N*-Alkylated and *C*-alkylated products can be produced via SN_2 (direct-alkylation) as well as through SN_1 (aniline with propene via carbenium ion) mechanisms.

Table 1. Alkylation of aniline by isopropanol over base zeolites

Aniline : isopropanol = 1 : 1 (mole), weight of catalyst = 4 g

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Flow rate ml/h	Mole% conversion of aniline	Mole% selectivity of products		
				(A)	(B)	(C)
Li-Y	350	10	12.5	35	57.5	8.4
Na-Y	350	10	9.6	42.2	51.3	6.5
K-Y	350	10	7.6	50.7	43.4	8.9
Ca-Y	350	10	17.7	44.4	48.4	7.2
Sr-Y	350	10	14.2	48	46	6
Ba-Y	350	10	12.6	52.7	40	7.3
Ba-Y	350	20	10.3	56	39	5
Ba-Y	350	30	7.4	59	36.5	4.5
Ba-Y	350	40	5.3	64	32	4
Ba-Y	200	10	8.6	50	44	6
Ba-Y	250	10	9.8	47	46	7
Ba-Y	300	10	10.4	45	47.5	7.5
Ba-Y	400	10	14.5	42	50	8
Ba-Y	450	10	19.2	40	52.6	7.4

*(A) = *N*-isopropylaniline; (B) = *o*-isopropylaniline; (C) = *p*-isopropylaniline.

It is known that alkali cation exchanged zeolites have little activity to promote any reactions proceeding through carbonium ion intermediate. It is also reported³ that lithium exchanged zeolite always has the highest catalytic activity among the alkali metal cations in dehydration, isomerization and dealkylation reactions. Hence it can be speculated that Li-Y zeolites favours SN_1 mechanism for alkylation rather than SN_2 mechanism.

It is suggested that *N*-alkylation selectivity increases with basicity of catalyst. *C*-Alkylation selectivity decreased from Li to K exchanged zeolites while *N*-alkylation selectivity increases with increase in basic nature of alkaline earth metal ion exchanged zeolites.

The effect of rate of flow was also studied. As expected, the conversion of aniline decreased with increase in flow rate (decrease in contact time, Table 1). The selectivity towards *N*-alkylation increased with increase in flow rate but that towards *ortho*-isomer decreased. This indicates that with the increase of contact time the isomerization of *N*-isopropylaniline increases. This latter reaction has been earlier reported⁵.

The reactions were performed at 200, 250, 300, 350, 400 and 450° to understand the effect of temperature on the conversion and selectivity. The conversion increased with increase in temperature. The yield of *N*-isopropylaniline decreased with increase in temperature, whereas the yield of *C*-alkylated products increased with increase in temperature. It is shown that high temperature favours isomerization and dealkylation of *N*-isopropylaniline. The studies on effect of temperature and effect of contact time clearly reveal that *C*-alkylated products are formed by direct alkylation through SN_2 mechanism, as well as reaction between aniline and propene via SN_1 mechanism and by isomerization of *N*-isopropylaniline over ion exchanged zeolites.

Experimental

Lithium, potassium and calcium cation exchanged zeolites obtained from NaY type were prepared by ion exchanged procedure⁸ using 0.5 *N* aqueous solutions of the

metal chlorides. Strontium and barium ion exchanged zeolites were prepared using 0.5 *N* aqueous solutions of the metal nitrates. After the exchange process the catalysts were washed with distilled water, dried at 110° for 4 h and then calcined at 450° for 6 h in a stream of dry air.

The cationic contents of these catalysts were analyzed by using inductively coupled plasma techniques. The crystallinity of these samples were determined by X-ray diffraction. Experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure with a fixed bed down flow pyrex glass reactor (2.5 cm dia, 40 cm length) kept in a furnace. The catalyst (4 g) in powder form (used without binder) was kept in the middle isothermal region of the reactor. The space above the catalyst was packed with pyrex glass beads which acted as a pre-heated zone. The catalyst was activated at 450° in a flow of dry air and the temperature was brought to the reaction temperature in a stream of pure air. The liquid mixture was introduced to the reactor at a predetermined flow rate. The liquid products were cooled, condensed and analysed by a gas chromatograph using a 5 m 10% carbowax column. The products were characterised by IR, PMR and mass spectra. A blank run was also conducted at 350°.

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